

Still Excited After 28 Years

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Twenty-eight years have come and gone,
Yet my excitement still lives on.
When school days near and classes start,
A happy feeling fills my heart.

New faces come, new dreams take flight,
The campus feels alive and bright.
The classrooms may look the same each year,
But fresh beginnings still draw near.

I've taught so long, yet I still find
New lessons waiting in each mind.
The joy of guiding, day by day,
Has never really gone away.

The books, the plans, the classroom cheer,
Still make me smile when July is near.
Though time has passed and seasons flew,
The thrill of teaching still feels new.

Some count the years and slow their pace,
But I still love this special place.
For every class that comes my way,
Reminds me why I chose to stay.

And so I welcome another year,
With grateful heart and hopeful cheer.
After twenty-eight years in service true,
The excitement remains, steady and new.

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